

Majhera 3, a drought-tolerant variety

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During kharif 1978, 3 upland trials consisting of 121 early maturing entries were direct-seeded at the Rice Research

Station, Majhera. Intermittent drought periods of 8, 9, and 10 days, separated by 5- to 6-day intervals, occurred during the vegetative growth stage. At the reproductive and grain-filling stages, drought struck twice for periods of 14 and 6 days, separated by a 4-day interval.

At maturity only the variety Majhera 3, a selection from the local variety Jaulia, matured and had good

seed setting. None of the other 120 varieties performed well, although a few had seed setting. Majhera 3 is a tall, nonlodging type in uplands. Its medium slender grain has straw-colored husk and a red pericarp. It is susceptible to both leaf and neck blast. Its drought tolerance should be tested in other agroclimatic regions. □

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Research on varietal tolerance for phosphorus-deficient rice soils

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Phosphorus (P) deficiency appears to be the most widespread of several soil mineral stresses that limit rice yields in many rice-growing countries. Recent screening has shown that some varieties are tolerant of P deficiency. Use of varietal tolerance to stabilize rice yields would be simpler and less expensive than P amendment, especially in soils with mild mineral deficiencies.

IRRI conducted a performance test on a P-deficient soil (available P, 2 ppm) in the 1978 dry season at Pangil, Laguna province, Philippines, to measure how much P deficiency reduces yields and to assess the potential of varietal tolerance. Twenty-four tolerant and susceptible genotypes of comparable growth duration were used in the test. Rices tolerant of P deficiency were chosen after careful review of screening results for several seasons. The susceptible rices chosen had all exhibited high yield potential in rice yield trials. Half of the experimental site, referred to as P₁, received a basal application of 25 kg P₂O₅/ha. The untreated half was P₀. Eighteen-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 3 February 1978 at 25- × 25-cm spacing at 60 hills/plot, in

a randomized complete block design replicated S times on P₀ and P₁. A basal application of urea at 50 kg N/ha was made at final land preparation. Recommended management practices were followed until maturity. The entries were scored for injury due to P deficiency on 17 March and 8 May. Grain, yield and ancillary characters, such as number of panicles, straw weight,

and P content of grain and straw were recorded.

Treatment differences in yield were significant at both P levels (see table). For P₁ the yields ranged from 2.6 to 4.3 t/ha (mean, 3.9 t/ha); for P₀, they ranged from 3.6 to 4.0 t/ha (mean, 3.3 t/ha). The yield was 15% lower in P₀ than in P₁. The yield depression ranged from 4.3 to 26.7% for individual varieties. But

Performance of 24 rices on a phosphorus (P)-deficient soil at Pangil, Laguna province, Philippines, 1978 dry season.

Designation	Grain yield ^a (g/plot)		Yield difference ^b (%) (P ₁ -P ₀)
	P ₁	P ₀	
IR8	791 cdefg	736 abcd	7.0
IR34	877 a	812 a	7.4*
IR40	786 cdefg	620 efghi	21.1*
IR1514A-E666	784 cdefg	585 ghij	25.4**
IR1623-93-2-2	759 defg	619 efghi	18.4**
IR2061-628-1-6-4-3	841 abcd	713 bcde	15.4**
IR2307-84-2-1	797 bcdefg	672 cdefg	15.7*
IR2797-105-2-2	875 ab	709 bcdef	19.0**
IR2797-105-2-2-3	795 cdefg	761 abc	4.3
IR2823-103-5-1A	848 abc	732 abcd	13.7**
IR2823-103-5-1B	849 abc	741 abcd	12.7**
IR2863-35-3-3	792 cdefg	688 ef	13.1**
IR3449-172-2	718 g	611 fghi	14.9*
IR4219-35-3	528 h	516 j	2.3
IR4422-51-6-3	784 cdefg	575 ghij	26.7**
IR4427-58-5-2A	808 abcdef	671 cdefgh	17.0*
IR4427-58-5-28	794 cdefg	670 cdefgh	15.6*
IR4427-315-2-3	764 defg	695 bcdef	9.0
IR4432-38-6-5-2	740 fg	644 defghi	13.0*
IR4707-123-3A	760 defg	571 ij	24.9**
IR4707-123-3B	756 efg	630 efghi	16.7*
IR4816-70-1	822 abcdef	685 ef	16.7*
IR5105-93-2-2	771 cdefg	669 cdefgh	13.2
BR51-91-6	834 abcde	790 ab	5.3

^aP₁ received a basal application of 25 kg P₂O₅/ha. P₀ received no P. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b*Significant at 5% level; **significant at 1% level.